

The TRevolution Profile

Authors: Rob Baxter, Antony Chuter, Christian Cole, Alexander Hambley, Simon Li, Tim Machin, Gordon Milligan, Phil Quinlan, Jim Smith, Stian Soiland-Reyes, Simon Thompson

1. Background

Version 1.0 of the SATRE (October 2023) specification has been well received by the UK TRE and sensitive research data community. It has been adopted by industry service providers as well as national and regional TREs across the UK. TRevolution will refresh and update SATRE to adapt to feedback collected since the release of v1.0 and incorporate missing aspects of the core components. In particular, any consideration for a federated network of TREs is not considered nor included within the specification. Important aspects of metadata capturing and statistical disclosure have also not been fully incorporated into the current version of the specification.

2. Future Direction

Version 2.0 will be updated to formalise the TRevolution Profile by introducing a fifth capability pillar building extensions suitable for federation of TREs. Through engagement with the UK, and potentially international, TRE community we will develop the new pillar aspects around the concepts described above on a "Front-Door" TRE, "Node" TRE and "Compute and Execution" Nodes such as briefly described below and in Figure 1.

Figure 1: SATRE core Pillars and Capabilities with the addition of the Federation Pillar

2.1 Capabilities (Broader SATRE)

As described above the SATRE 2.0 specification broadens the architecture to include a “Federation Pillar” and integrate the Federated Architecture Blueprint ([DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint](#)).

The specification will be reviewed and implementation statements updated to define a universal specification for a community of interconnected TREs as described in the TREvolution profile above.

We will continue the same process as version 1.0 where we engaged with the community and reflected the needs and voices of the TRE community while taking into account public opinion.

2.2 Unified Designs (Deeper SATRE)

SATRE 2.0 will unify lower level designs for components of TREvolution beyond the capabilities, components and specification of SATRE 1.0. This may include process flows, (meta)data models and infrastructure designs implemented by the other products. As shown in Figure 2 we will work together with the DARE UK Early Adopters that have an interest in SATRE which are VISTA, PANORAMA, FRIDGE and FOCUS-5.

Figure 2: A SATRE Unified Design

3. Enhancements for Federation

A core component of TRevolution is the creation of federation capacity within a network of member TREs. Figure 3 shows a high-level schematic of the TRevolution Profile showing the core components and interactions with services and federated TREs.

Figure 3: TRevolution federation high-level view

A federated project will have resources (governance, data, compute) spread across different organisations, all federated analyses have to start somewhere, both from a technical initiation (i.e. pressing Go) but also from a governance perspective, in terms of a location knowing that this a federated project that has been approved, what resources it should consume, what data it should access and what TREs are involved.

We are proposing that all federated analytics or federated learning is initiated from within a TRE. This means we are not going to accept federated analytics and learning where the query initiates from the outside world. This requirement may relax over time but is a prudent protection in the first instance.

Therefore, we need a TRE that will take the technical and governance responsibility to initiate a federated project, referred to as a “Front Door TRE”. We do not expect all TREs to want to undertake this role, as it involves taking on the responsibility for the project as a whole. Therefore, a **Front Door TRE** will require to have:

Governance, Permissions, and Researcher Validation

- A mechanism for recording which TREs are part of the federated project

- A mechanism for validating a Safe Person in the context of the federated Safe Project
- A mechanism to validate the researcher is only seeking to access TREs for which the federated project has permissions

Disclosure Control and Risk Management

- A mechanism for recording the disclosure control sensitivities for each TRE in a project
- A mechanism to apply and ensure the disclosure rules of all member TREs has been applied before any results leave the Front Door TRE
- A mechanism for providing the researcher with a disclosure risk analysis of their query outputs - which in most cases will necessarily be conducted at the time the query is executed.

Federated Access, Querying, and Researcher Environment

- A mechanism for providing an environment to the researcher that can access multiple TREs (directly or indirectly)
- A mechanism for providing the researcher with the ability to query (meta)data in multiple TREs
- A mechanism to facilitate the researcher with access to the network of TREs

Workflow Orchestration and Data/Analysis Exchange

- A mechanism to receive, process and pass on an analytics container with other TREs
- A mechanism to receive responses from each TRE once the analysis has completed
- A mechanism to send configurations for a project to a Node TRE for the purpose of the project, as per the agreed specification

Researcher Support and Feedback

- A mechanism for demonstrating capabilities and data availability at participating node TREs to researchers
- A mechanism for providing the researcher with a status update of the analysis

A “Node TRE” in contrast only has responsibility for their own involvement in the federated project. Therefore, their role is to:

Infrastructure Integration & Connectivity

- Provide a mechanism for a Front Door TRE to connect to their infrastructure
- Provide a mechanism to apply configurations for a project sent by the Front Door TRE

Federated Access, Querying, and Researcher Environment

- Provide a mechanism for analyses to be processed within their infrastructure
- Provide a mechanism for the Front Door TRE to include their data in a federated view of data

Disclosure Control and Risk Management

- Provide a mechanism to provide the Front Door TRE with their approvals and disclosure control requirements
- Provide a mechanism to apply disclosure risk assessment using their local risk appetites, and report the same to the Front door TRE in a standardised format. (This is needed for all forms of Federated Machine Learning and some, but not all, forms of federated analytics.)

A “**Compute and Execution Node**” is solely responsible for processing a job, therefore, their role is to:

- Provide a mechanism for a Front Door TRE to connect to their infrastructure
- Provide a mechanism to apply configurations for a project sent by the Front Door TRE
- Provide a mechanism for analyses to be processed within their infrastructure

Standard TRE:

- A mechanism for providing the researcher with a disclosure risk analysis of their query outputs - at the time of query.

4. Metadata Enhancements

- Overall, support for the SATRE *Observability* principle using FAIR methods provides systematic and programmatically accessible observation data, e.g. for a TRE dashboard. However, to support meaningful aggregation and queries over this metadata, additional contextual information from TREs have to be captured, even if not directly required for computational purposes. SATRE should more explicitly endorse use of common metadata/provenance standards for TRE interoperability.
- SATRE should introduce an optional component under Section 4.3 to specify maintaining machine-readable records of analyses

5. Disclosure Control Enhancements

The ‘statbarns’ taxonomy ([Green, Ritchie and White 2023](#)) collated decades of research, guidance, and operational practice into a conceptual framework for categorising different types of outputs (tables, figures, models etc.) into classes which have associated risks, measures, and mitigations. Within TREvolution these are being *captured* via [design diagrams](#), *formalised* in machine-actionable form (using the W3C Data Privacy Vocabulary), and *extended* to cover AI risks and mitigations. The diagram representations will be co-designed with the community to maximise transparency and value Public, Data Owners and Information Governance managers and TRE staff.

The formal frameworks built from the design diagrams are designed to facilitate:

SDC1. Statements of the capabilities provided by different disclosure control tools. For example, tools vary in the *types* of output they support, *risks* they assess for a given type of output, and the choices of *mitigations* they provide for different risks.

SDC2. Informed choices by TREs about appropriate tools for different projects.

SDC3. Tool-agnostic statements of TRE risk appetites and preferred mitigations at the project level

On this basis we can define the following set of capabilities that a TRE should provide if they wish to support any form of (semi-) automated disclosure risk assessment. These capabilities will be **necessary** if they wish to support the use and egress of trained AI models and **recommended** if the TRE wishes to support any form of federated learning. In most cases these are relatively minor additions/clarifications of existing SATRE specifications

A single-site TRE without federation

- SATRE v1 specifications 3.1.2, 3.3.1, 3.3.2, 3.3.6, 3.3.7, 3.3.8 are now **mandatory**. In particular the 'system to classify outputs (3.3.1) should conform to the formal framework described above.
- Must provide a 'risk appetite' (SDC3) for each project for auditing and SDC purposes. This should include preferred mitigations -especially in the case of AI models
- Must have a documented process for identifying and handling disclosure risks associated with any outputs that are not automatically checked by the chosen toolset. This is the inverse of 3.3.5, to prevent over-reliance on 'incomplete' tools/mitigations. Gap analysis should be supported via a combination of SDC1-3 and SATRE specification 3.3.2 (identify outputs).

A TRE acting as a node in a federation should have the above plus:

- Individual nodes must provide a statement of risk appetite (SDC1) to the front door node. This should include:
 - Whether the TRE chooses to devolve approval to the front-door TRE output checkers
 - Which other nodes in a federation the TRE is satisfied do not contain duplicates of their data - e.g., if a person moves between regions- which could invalidate SDC mitigations.
- Individual nodes should have the capacity to flag that results being returned are the potentially disclosive and must not be released without additional risk assessment
- Individual nodes should have the capacity to perform automated disclosure checks on request and return these with query results to the front door TRE.
- Front door nodes must support an 'aggregator' to
 - Receive partial query results and risks assessments from nodes
 - Reason about, and make recommendations for, approvals needed based on individual TREs risk appetites
- Collectively, each node in a federation should explicitly support separation between:
 - Data manipulation commands- which *may* produce simple 'completion status' feedback that will not be disclosive

- 'Intermediate Query results' that are flagged as potentially disclosive and, **may** be presented to researcher (depending on risk appetite) or their code (for iterated learning) but **never** be released;
- 'Output Query' results that form 'outputs' and **may** be released subject to passing appropriate disclosure checks.

6. Implementation

6.1 Collaboration Cafés

Starting May 2025 a series of regular [Collaboration Cafés](#) will be announced. They will cover a range of TRevolution-specific projects that require input and engagement from the public as well as the wider TRE community including the DARE UK Interest Groups and Early Adopter projects. This process was very successful previously and aided rapid engagement to hear a large number of voices.

We will run fortnightly online Cafés for up to six months in the first instance with topics announced in advance. They will be advertised widely with no requirement to register or sign-up ensuring easy access to the events.

6.2 Change Management

Updates and changes to the SATRE specification to encompass the TRevolution Profile can be suggested by anyone who engages with the project. They will be collated by the TRevolution team and managed as github issues. They will then be triaged for relevance and importance and a team decision made regarding whether or not to include the change in the Profile and/or SATRE.

6.3 Reference TRE Infrastructure as Code

The TRevolution Profile will take a significant step beyond the SATRE project by creating a reference implementation which encapsulates all the core components as an infrastructure-as-code solution for other organisations to use. This will be a formal implementation of the SATRE specification built from the ground up for the first time.

As with all aspects of TRevolution, the core components and services will be usable independently such that external implementers can choose the components and services that fit their needs best.

6.4 Transparency

All engagement and decisions made on implementation will be done in the open through public documentation and/or use of open access tools such as github. For example, all SATRE specification changes and requests for changes will be captured using [github issues](#). All other TRevolution open access software and tooling can be found on the DARE UK [github page](#).